

1 **Homing Peptide-Based Targeting of Tenascin-C and Fibronectin in Endometriosis**

2 Lorena Simón-Gracia^{1,+}, Kristina Kiisholts^{2,+}, Vilma Petrikaite^{3,4}, Allan Tobi¹, Merli Saare^{2,5}, Prakash
3 Lingasamy¹, Maire Peters^{2,5}, Andres Salumets^{2,5,6,7}, Tambet Teesalu^{1,8,*}

4 ⁺ Both authors contributed equally to this work.

5 ¹ Laboratory of Precision and Nanomedicine. Department of Biomedicine and Translational Medicine.
6 University of Tartu

7 ² Competence Centre on Health Technologies, Tartu, Estonia

8 ³ Laboratory of Drug Target Histopathology, Institute of Cardiology, Lithuanian University of Health
9 Sciences, Kaunas, Lithuania

10 ⁴ Institute of Biotechnology, Life Sciences Center, Vilnius University, Lithuania

11 ⁵ Department of Obstetrics and Gynecology, Institute of Clinical Medicine, University of Tartu, Tartu,
12 Estonia

13 ⁶ Institute of Genomics, University of Tartu, Tartu, Estonia

14 ⁷ Division of Obstetrics and Gynecology, Department of Clinical Science, Intervention and Technology
15 (CLINTEC), Karolinska Institutet, Stockholm, Sweden

16 ⁸ Center for Nanomedicine and Department of Cell, Molecular and Developmental Biology, University of
17 California at Santa Barbara, Santa Barbara, California 93106

18 * Corresponding author: tambet.teesalu@ut.ee

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1 **ABSTRACT**

2 The current diagnostic and therapeutic strategies for endometriosis are limited. Although endometriosis
3 is a benign condition, some of its traits, such as increased cell invasion, migration, tissue inflammation,
4 and angiogenesis are similar to cancer. Here we explored the application of homing peptides for precision
5 delivery of diagnostic and therapeutic compounds to endometriotic lesions. First, we audited a panel of
6 peptide phages for the binding to the cultured immortalized endometriotic epithelial 12Z and eutopic
7 stromal HESC cell lines. The bacteriophages displaying PL1 peptide that engages with angiogenic
8 extracellular matrix overexpressed in solid tumors showed the strongest binding to both cell lines. The
9 receptors of PL1 peptide, tenascin C domain C (TNC-C) and fibronectin Extra Domain-B (Fn-EDB), were
10 expressed in both cells. Silver nanoparticles functionalized with synthetic PL1 peptide showed specific
11 internalization in 12Z and HESC cells. Treatment with PL1-nanoparticles loaded with the potent antimetabolic
12 drug monomethyl auristatin E decreased the viability of endometriotic cells in 2D and 3D cultures. Finally,
13 PL1-nanoparticles bound to the cryosections of clinical peritoneal endometriotic lesions in the areas
14 positive for TNC-C and Fn-EDB immunoreactivities, and not to sections of normal endometrium. Our
15 findings suggest potential applications for PL1-guided nanoparticles in precision diagnosis and therapy of
16 endometriosis.

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19 **Keywords:** endometriosis, homing peptide, silver nanoparticles, nanomedicine, extracellular matrix

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1 INTRODUCTION

2 In endometriosis, the endometrial glandular epithelial and stromal cells establish outgrowths outside the
3 uterine tissue throughout the abdominal–pelvic peritoneum and visceral organs¹. Endometriosis affects
4 ~5–10% of women in reproductive age, and it is a frequent source of infertility and chronic pelvic pain².
5 Available treatments (painkillers, laparoscopic resection of endometriotic lesions, and hormonal
6 treatments such as contraceptives, gonadotropin releasing hormone agonists (GnRHa), and antagonists)
7 only alleviate the symptoms of the disease and/or are associated with serious side effects³. For example,
8 hormonal treatments are effective in pain reduction, but cause frequent hyperandrogenic side effects and
9 are not suitable if the woman desires pregnancy³. In cases where patients are refractory to treatment
10 with oral contraceptives, progestins, GnRHa, and aromatase inhibitors are used, but these therapies have
11 a high rate of adverse effects⁴. Although laparoscopy can temporarily alleviate the symptoms, complete
12 excision of the lesions remains challenging, leading to recurrence over time⁵.

13 Despite its benign clinical behavior and normal-appearing histological features, endometriosis shares
14 some characteristics with malignant processes, such as increased cell proliferation, migration, invasion
15 and resistance to apoptosis⁶. Some mutations present in malignant neoplasms are also found in
16 endometriotic lesions⁷. Moreover, some extracellular matrix (ECM) proteins upregulated in solid tumors
17 are overexpressed in ectopic endometrium. ECM is involved in the modulation of cellular adhesion and
18 invasion, and aberrant cell-ECM interactions may be functionally involved in the progression of
19 endometriosis⁸. For example, the ECM molecule tenascin C (TNC) and its spliced variants play an important
20 role in neovascularization, modulation of cell adhesion, and cell migration⁹. In endometriotic lesions, the
21 expression of TNC is upregulated and, unlike in eutopic endometrium, TNC expression in the lesions is not
22 dependent on the menstrual cycle^{10,11}. Spliced isoforms of fibronectin are also overexpressed in human
23 endometriotic lesions¹². Expression of alternatively spliced fibronectin Extra Domain-A and B (Fn-EDA and
24 Fn-EDB) isoforms is associated with perturbations such as upregulation of cell proliferation, angiogenesis
25 and tumor metastasis¹³, and Fn-EDA has been used as a target for affinity-based delivery to endometriotic
26 lesions¹². Due to their robust overexpression in solid tumors, TNC-C and Fn-EDB are considered promising
27 targets for precision delivery of therapeutics and imaging agents to malignant lesions^{14,15}. Recently, we
28 reported the identification and characterization of a panel of homing peptides that target tumor ECM: a
29 peptide that binds to TNC-C and Fn-EDB (PL1 peptide)¹⁶, to Fn-EDB and neuropilin-1 (NRP-1) (PL2
30 peptide)¹⁷, and to TNC-C and NRP-1 (PL3 peptide)¹⁸. Systemic PL1- and PL3-guided therapeutic

1 nanoparticles reduced the progression of glioblastoma xenografts and increased the survival of tumor-
2 bearing mice^{16,18}.

3 In the current study, we investigated the therapeutic potential of homing peptide-based targeting of
4 endometriosis. Using a phage pool displaying a panel of known peptides, binding studies were carried out
5 with cultured immortalized endometriotic cells, which demonstrated a robust binding and internalization
6 of PL1 peptide-displaying phages. Silver nanoparticles (AgNPs) functionalized with synthetic PL1 peptide
7 bound to and penetrated into endometriotic cells in 2D and 3D cultures. As a proof-of-concept efficacy
8 study, we demonstrated the ability of AgNPs loaded with the antimetabolic drug monomethyl auristatin E
9 (MMAE)¹⁹ to suppress the viability of endometriotic cells cultured in 2D and as spheroids in a peptide-
10 dependent manner. Finally, in a cryosections overlay assay, we observed preferential accumulation of
11 PL1-nanoparticles in Fn-EDB- and TNC-C-positive regions of human endometriosis samples.

12 These studies suggest a potential application for PL1-guided precision drugs, imaging agents, and
13 nanoparticles for the detection and therapy of endometriosis.

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1 MATERIALS AND METHODS

2 Materials

3 Oligonucleotides were purchased from Integrated DNA Technologies IDT (USA). Biotinylated peptides (see
4 Table 1) were purchased from TAG Copenhagen, Denmark. Tripotassium hexacyanoferrate(III) ($K_3Fe(CN)_6$;
5 CAS# 13746-66-2), sodium thiosulfate pentahydrate ($Na_2S_2O_3$; CAS# 10102-17-7), Tween-20,
6 paraformaldehyde (PFA), Triton-X, NP40 (IGEPAL® CA-630), LB medium, and 4',6-diamidino-2-
7 phenylindole (DAPI) were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich, Germany. IPTG was purchased from Carbosynth
8 Limited, UK. Dulbecco's Modified Eagle Medium (DMEM) and phosphate-buffered saline pH 7.4 (PBS)
9 were purchased from Lonza, Belgium. DMEM/F-12 medium with HEPES and without phenol red, McCoy's
10 5A Medium with HEPES, Penicillin, Streptomycin, TrypLE Express Enzyme without phenol red, and Trypan
11 Blue stain were purchased from Gibco, Thermo Fischer Scientific, USA. CellStripper Dissociation Reagent
12 was purchased from Corning, Thermo Fischer Scientific, USA. Bovine serum albumin (BSA), fetal bovine
13 serum (FBS), and charcoal stripped FBS were purchased from Capricorn Scientific, Germany. Goat serum
14 was purchased from GE Healthcare, UK. For the synthesis and functionalization of silver nanoparticles
15 (AgNPs), $AgNO_3$ (#209139), trisodium citrate hydrate (#25114), 4-morpholineethanesulfonic acid
16 hemisodium salt (#M0164), tris(2-carboxyethyl)phosphine hydrochloride solution (TCEP; #646547), the
17 dye CF555 succinimidyl ester (NHS-CF555, #SCJ4600022), and dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO) were purchased
18 from Sigma-Aldrich. NeutrAvidin (#31055) was purchased from Thermo Scientific, OPSS-PEG(5K)-SCM
19 linker from JenKem Technology USA, and lipoic acid-PEG(1K)-NH₂ (#PG2-AMLA-1k) from Nanocs. OSu-
20 Glu-Val-Cit-PAB-monomethyl auristatin E (NHS-MMAE-linker) was purchased from Concortis
21 Biotherapeutics, California, USA.

Peptide ID	Sequence	Receptor	Reference
PL1	PPRRGLIKLKTS	TNC-C and Fn-EDB	16
PL2	TSKQNSR	Fn-EDB and NRP-1	17
PL3	AGRGLVR	TNC-C and NRP-1	18
RPAR	RPARPAR	NRP-1	20
iRGD	C*RGDKGPDC*	Integrin $\alpha\beta_{3/5}$ and NRP1 after cleavage	21
EM1	VRRADNRPG	Cyclic nucleotide-gated channel β_3 (CNGB3)	22
EM2	RTRLHTR	Unknown	23

22 **Table 1. Sequences of the peptides used.** *Disulfide bound

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2 **Cell culture**

3 Human immortalized endometriotic epithelial 12Z (cat. No T0764) and human immortalized endometrial
4 stromal HESC (cat. No T0533) cells were purchased from ABM (USA). 12Z cells were cultured in DMEM
5 supplemented with 10% FBS, 100 U/mL penicillin, and 100 µg/mL streptomycin. HESC cells were cultured
6 in DMEM/F-12 medium without phenol red that was supplemented with 10% Charcoal-stripped FBS, 100
7 U/mL penicillin, and 100 µg/mL streptomycin. During cell passaging, CellStripper dissociation reagent was
8 used for 12Z and TrypLE Express Enzyme without phenol red for HESC detachment. Cells were grown at
9 37 °C, 5% CO₂ in a humidified environment.

10 **Phage binding to cultured 12Z and HESC cells**

11 Peptide-displaying T7 bacteriophages were prepared by cloning nucleotide sequences coding for different
12 peptides into phage genomic DNA to be expressed on the phage surface as C-terminal fusions to capsid
13 protein. The complementary oligonucleotides were annealed and the cloning was performed according
14 to the manufacturer's protocol using the T7Select[®] 415-1 Cloning Kit (Millipore, 70015-3). Peptide-
15 displaying phage clones were thereafter amplified in complementing host bacterial cells BLT5403 and
16 purified with polyethylene glycol according to an established protocol²⁴.

17 Prior to phage addition, 12Z and HESC cells were detached, washed with PBS, and resuspended in 0.5%
18 BSA containing DMEM. Phages expressing a single peptide of interest (5×10^7 PFU/mL) were added to $5 \times$
19 10^7 cells, wherein insertless phage was used as a negative control. Incubation with phage clones was
20 carried out on a slowly rocking platform at 4 °C for 1 h. Cells were washed four times with 0.5% BSA
21 containing DMEM to eliminate unbound phages. Finally, the cells together with bound phages were
22 resuspended in 1% NP40 containing LB solution, and plaque assay was performed as described earlier²⁴.
23 Briefly, the amount of phage in cell lysates was determined by titering using Escherichia coli strain
24 BLT5615 in LB medium containing 2 mM IPTG.

25 **Synthesis and functionalization of AgNPs**

26 The AgNPs were synthesized according to the citrate method of Lee and Meisel²⁵. Surface
27 functionalization of AgNPs was carried out as previously published^{19,26}, wherein biotinylated peptides
28 were used as the targeting moiety, CF555 dye as the fluorophore, and MMAE-linker as a therapeutic
29 payload. Briefly, AgNO₃ (360 mg) was dissolved in high resistivity water (2 L; resistivity 18 MΩ cm⁻¹) in a

1 flask cleaned with piranha solution ($\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4/\text{H}_2\text{O}_2$). Next, trisodium citrate hydrate (400 mg) was dissolved
2 in high resistivity water (40 mL) and added to the vessel. The solution was boiled in the dark for 30 min.
3 The resulting Ag-citrate was used directly in the next step. Simultaneously, NeutrAvidin (NA) was modified
4 with an OPSS-PEG(5K)-SCM linker (OPSS) according to the procedure described by Braun *et al*²⁶. Next,
5 NeutrAvidin-OPSS (3.9 mL, 2.9 mg/mL) was added to the Ag-citrate solution (500 mL). After 2 min, 4-
6 morpholineethanesulfonic acid hemisodium salt (5 mL, 0.5 M in high resistivity water) was added. The pH
7 of the solution was adjusted to 6.0 and the solution was kept at 37 °C for 24 h. The solution was brought
8 to room temperature (RT) and 10X phosphate-buffered saline (50 mL) was added, followed by Tween-20
9 (250 μL). The solution was centrifuged at $12,200 \times g$ at 4 °C for 1 h, the supernatant was removed, and
10 the particles were resuspended in PBST (0.005% Tween-20 in PBS). Next, TCEP solution was added to a
11 final concentration of 1 mM, followed by incubation at RT for 30 min. Then lipoic acid-PEG(1K)-NH₂ was
12 added to a final concentration of 5 μM , and the mixture was incubated at RT for 2.5 h. The solution was
13 centrifuged at $17,200 \times g$ at 4 °C for 20 min, the supernatant was removed and the particles were
14 resuspended in PBST at half of the initial volume. The AgNP solution was filtered through a 0.45 μm filter
15 and stored at 4 °C in dark.

16 NHS-CF555 dye or NHS-functionalized MMAE-linker was coupled to the amino groups of the linker on the
17 AgNPs. For this, NHS-CF555 or NHS-MMAE-linker (5 μL , 2 mM) in DMSO was added to AgNPs (500 μL),
18 followed by incubation at 4 °C overnight. The particles were washed 3 times by centrifugation at $3,500 \times$
19 g at 4 °C for 10 min, followed by resuspension of the particles in PBST by sonication. Next, biotinylated
20 peptides were coupled to the particles by adding the peptide (10 μL , 2 mM in high resistivity water) to
21 AgNPs (500 μL), followed by incubation at RT for 30 min. The AgNPs were washed, 0.2 μm filtered and
22 stored in the dark at 4 °C.

23 **Characterization of AgNPs**

24 For transmission electron microscopy (TEM), the AgNPs were diluted in MQ water, dropped onto the
25 carbon film-covered side of a copper Cu-300 TEM grids (Agar Scientific, Ltd, Essex, UK), air-dried, and
26 imaged with a Tecnai-10 transmission electron microscope (FEI, Oregon, USA) at 80 kV. The concentration
27 of AgNPs was calculated according to the Beer-Lambert law by measuring the UV-Vis absorbance of
28 AgNPs at 415 nm and using a molar attenuation coefficient of $8.83 \times 10^{-9} \text{ M}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$. For size and zeta
29 potential measurements, the AgNPs were diluted 400X in MQ water. Zetasizer Pro (Malvern Panalytical,
30 UK) was used for the measurements. Size measurements were done at 25 °C with the material refractive
31 index (RI) set to 2.00, and material absorption set to 0.200 using polystyrene cuvettes (#DTS0012,

1 Malvern); zeta potential measurements were done at 25 °C with 12 runs/measurement using capillary cell
2 cuvettes (#DTS1070, Malvern).

3 **Expression analysis of peptide receptors in cultured 12Z and HESC cells**

4 The expression of peptide receptors on 2D cultured cells was studied using immunofluorescence staining.
5 12Z and HESC cells (100,000 cells) were seeded onto noncoated coverslips (12 mm diameter, Marienfeld-
6 Superior) in a 24-well plate and cultured for 24 h. The cells were washed with PBS, fixed with 4% PFA in
7 PBS for 10 min, and incubated with a blocking buffer (5% BSA, 5% FBS, and 5% goat serum in PBS) at RT
8 for 30 min. The cells were incubated with a solution of rabbit polyclonal anti-TNC-C (15 µg/mL), rabbit
9 polyclonal anti-Fn-EDB (20 µg/mL), mouse monoclonal anti-NRP-1 (6 µg/mL)^{16,18} or mouse anti-integrin α
10 [272-17E6] (ab16821, Abcam) (5 µg/mL) antibodies in blocking buffer diluted 1:5 in PBS at RT for 30 min.
11 After washes with PBS, the cells were incubated with Alexa Fluor[®]647-goat anti-rabbit IgG (A21245,
12 Invitrogen, USA) or Alexa Fluor[®]647 goat anti-mouse IgG (A21235, Life Technologies, USA) (4 µg/mL in
13 blocking buffer diluted 1 : 5) at RT for 30 min. Cells were stained with DAPI (2 µg/mL) for 10 min, mounted
14 with mounting medium (Fluoromount-G; Electron Microscopy Sciences) and visualized using a confocal
15 microscope FV1200MPE (Olympus, Japan) equipped with a UPlanSApo 60x/1.35na objective (Olympus,
16 Japan). The images were analyzed using Olympus FluoView Ver.4.2a Viewer software.

17 **Luminescence-Based Cellular Viability Assay**

18 12Z and HESC cells (10,000 cells) were cultured in white 96-well plates for 24 h. Cells were treated with
19 different concentrations of PL1-MMAE-AgNPs or biotin-MMAE-AgNPs at 37 °C for 2 h and washed with
20 full medium. Cells in fresh medium were cultured for an additional 48 or 72 h and the cell viability was
21 measured using the CellTiter-Glo[®] Luminescent Cell Viability Assay (#G7570, Promega Biotech AB)
22 following the manufacturer's protocol. Luminescence was measured with a Victor X5 Multilabel
23 Microplate Reader (Perkin Elmer, USA). The cell viability was calculated as % viability = (bioluminescence
24 of the sample) \times 100 / (bioluminescence of cells incubated only with the medium).

25 **AgNP interaction with cells in 2D and 3D cultures**

26 To study AgNP uptake in 2D cell culture, 12Z and HESC cells (100,000 cells) were seeded in 24-well plates
27 and cultivated for 24 h. Subsequently, the cells were incubated with CF555-labeled AgNPs (0.3 nM in
28 DMEM with 10% FBS) at 37 °C for 2 h, washed, treated with an etching solution (1mM of K₃Fe(CN)₆ and
29 Na₂S₂O₃ in PBS) at RT for 5 min, washed with PBS, and detached with non-enzymatic cell dissociation
30 buffer (Corning™ CellStripper Dissociation Reagent, Thermo Fisher Scientific). Cells in suspension were

1 collected by centrifugation at $300 \times g$ for 5 min, resuspended in 0.2 mL PBS and analyzed by flow cytometry
2 (BD Accuri C6 Plus, BD Biosciences). The data analysis was done using the same software.

3 For AgNP uptake and penetration studies in 3D cultures, 12Z cell spheroids were formed by using the
4 magnetic 3D bioprinting method²⁷. Briefly, 12Z cells at 70% confluency in a 6-well plate were loaded with
5 magnetic nanoparticles (Nanoshuttle, n3D Biosciences, Inc.) in a humidified atmosphere containing 5%
6 CO₂ at 37 °C for 8 h. Cells were trypsinized, centrifuged, and seeded into ultra-low attachment 96-well
7 plate in a volume of 100 μL (2,000 cells/well). The plate was placed on a magnetic drive and incubated in
8 a humidified atmosphere with 5% CO₂ at 37 °C for 2 days. Subsequently, the spheroids were incubated
9 with 0.3 nM of fluorescently labeled AgNPs for 1, 2, 4, or 20 h. To remove extracellular particles, spheroids
10 were treated with the etching solution, washed twice with PBS, fixed in 4% buffered PFA, and cell nuclei
11 were counterstained with DAPI. The AgNPs in spheroids were visualized using a confocal laser scanning
12 microscope (Olympus FluoView FV1000, Japan; 10x objective).

13

14 **Treatment of 12Z spheroids with cytotoxic AgNPs**

15 For the morphological studies, 12Z spheroids were cultured in the presence of 0.6 nM PL1-MMAE-AgNPs
16 or biotin-MMAE-AgNPs (60 nM of MMAE) in complete medium in a humidified atmosphere with 5% CO₂
17 at 37 °C. The effect of the treatment on the spheroid morphology was studied every 24 h using the
18 Olympus IX73 inverted microscope (Olympus Corporation).

19 For the quantitative viability studies, 12Z spheroids were incubated with different concentrations of PL1-
20 MMAE-AgNPs or biotin-MMAE-AgNPs for 72 h and the number of live cells was determined with a
21 luminescence-based cell viability kit (CellTiter-Glo®, Promega, USA), according to the manufacturer's
22 protocol. The luminescence was measured using a Tecan Infinite 200 microplate reader (Tecan Trading
23 AG, Switzerland). Cell viability in spheroids was calculated as % viability = (bioluminescence of the sample)
24 $\times 100 /$ (bioluminescence of cells incubated only with the medium).

25 **Clinical endometriosis sample collection and immunostaining**

26 Endometrial and endometriotic lesion tissues from the patient were collected during laparoscopy at the
27 Tartu University Hospital Women's Clinic. The patient was of reproductive age, 28 years old, had not
28 received any hormonal medication three months before the recruitment and was suffering from stage IV
29 endometriosis. Sample collection procedure was approved by the Research Ethics Committee of the

1 University of Tartu (approval No. 276/M-13, Tartu, Estonia) and informed written consent was obtained
2 from the participant.

3 Following resection, endometrial and peritoneal endometriosis samples were transferred to cold McCoy's
4 5A Medium. Tissues were snap-frozen in liquid nitrogen and stored in a -80°C freezer. Prior to
5 cryosectioning with a Leica CM1520 cryostat, the tissues were embedded in Tissue Freezing Medium
6 (Leica Biosystems, Germany). Tissue sections ($10\ \mu\text{m}$) were collected on SuperFrost Plus slides (Thermo
7 Fischer Scientific, USA) and stored at -20°C .

8 For immunofluorescence staining and AgNP binding experiments, sections were air-dried at RT for 20 min
9 followed by re-hydration in cold PBS. Sections were fixed in ice-cold absolute methanol for 10 min, washed
10 with PBS, and permeabilized with 0.2% Triton-X in PBS for 10 min. After washing with PBST (0.05% Tween-
11 20 in PBS), sections were incubated with 5% blocking buffer in PBST at RT for 1 h.

12 For immunofluorescence, the tissues were incubated with rabbit polyclonal anti-TNC-C ($30\ \mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$) or
13 rabbit polyclonal anti-Fn-EDB ($40\ \mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$) primary antibodies in blocking buffer diluted 1 : 5 in PBST at RT
14 for 1 h. After washes with PBST, tissues were incubated with Alexa Fluor[®]647-goat anti-rabbit IgG
15 (A21245, Invitrogen, USA) ($10\ \mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ in blocking buffer diluted 1 : 5) at RT for 30 min.

16 For AgNP binding, sections were incubated with CF555-labeled AgNPs ($1.5\ \text{nM}$ in blocking buffer diluted
17 1 : 5) at RT for 2 h. Tissues were washed with PBST and nuclei were counterstained with DAPI ($2\ \mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$)
18 for 10 min. The sections were mounted with mounting medium and visualized using a confocal microscope
19 FV1200MPE (Olympus, Japan) equipped with a UPlanSApo 10x/0.4na objective (Olympus, Japan). The
20 images were analyzed with Olympus FluoView Ver.4.2a Viewer software.

21 For immunohistochemistry, sections were air-dried at RT for 20 min followed by fixation in 4% PFA in PBS
22 for 10 min, washed in PBS, and processed in the automated tissue staining system Ventana Benchmark
23 Ultra (Roche, Switzerland). The sections were stained with anti-CD10 (CM129C, Clone 56C6; Biocare
24 Medical, USA) and anti-CD31 (M0823, Clone JC70A; Dako, Agilent Technologies, USA) antibodies. Both
25 antibodies were diluted 1 : 50 in Dako Real Antibody Diluent (Agilent Technologies, USA) and incubated
26 at 36°C for 32 min or 36 min with anti-CD10 or anti-CD31, respectively. OptiView DAB (Ventana Medical
27 Systems, USA) detection kit was used according to the manufacturer's guidelines for CD10, and Ultraview
28 DAB (Ventana Medical Systems, USA) for CD31 antibody visualization.

1 Hematoxylin and eosin staining was conducted on the Leica ST5020 automated tissue staining system
2 (Leica Biosystems, Germany) by using the ST Infinity H&E Staining System Kit (Leica Biosystems, Germany)
3 according to the manufacturer's protocol.

4 **Statistical analysis**

5 Statistical analysis was performed with Statistica 8 software (StatSoft, USA) using Fisher LSD and the one-
6 way ANOVA tests. The significance level was set at $p < 0.05$.

1 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

2 TNC-C and Fn-EDB targeting peptide-displaying phages bind to 12Z and HESC cells

3 Peptide phage biopanning has been used for identification of a multitude of peptides able to recognize
4 differentially expressed vascular markers in healthy tissues and at sites of disease (e.g. malignant,
5 inflammatory, atherosclerotic and neurodegenerative lesions).^{24,28,29} To map the landscape of homing
6 peptides potentially useful for targeting endometriotic lesions, we first studied the binding of a panel of
7 T7 phages displaying different tumor homing peptides to two cultured human cell lines which are
8 commonly used as models of endometriotic cells: 12Z (immortalized epithelial-like ectopic endometriotic
9 cells) and HESC (immortalized eutopic endometrial stromal cells) cells^{30,31}. These cell lines were chosen to
10 represent the stromal and the glandular epithelial compartments of the endometrium, both known to
11 play a role in the pathogenesis of endometriosis. Endometriosis, like cancer, is an angiogenesis-dependent
12 disease, and increased vasculature and newly formed blood vessels are often observed in areas
13 surrounding endometriotic lesions³². Factors involved in the promotion of vascular growth and
14 permeability, such as the vascular endothelial growth factor (VEGF), bradykinin, and reactive oxygen
15 species, are also associated with endometriosis³²⁻³⁴. As neovascularization is a shared hallmark in the
16 pathogenesis of both endometriosis and cancer, we included in the binding studies the homing peptides
17 that target molecules expressed in angiogenic vessels: PL1 (receptors: TNC-C and Fn-EDB), PL2 (Fn-EDB
18 and NRP-1), PL3 (TNC-C and NRP-1), prototypic C-end Rule (CendR) peptide RPARPAR, referred from now
19 as RPAR (NRP-1), and iRGD peptide (angiogenic α v integrins and NRP-1) (Table 1). In addition, we added
20 phages displaying two peptides reported to bind endometriotic lesions (VRRADNRPG and RTRLHTR that
21 we refer to as EM1 and EM2 peptides) (Table 1) and insertless phage as a negative control.

22 The phages displaying bispecific TNC-C and Fn-EDB targeting PL1 peptide showed the strongest binding to
23 both HESC and 12Z cells (13–16-fold over the insertless phage) (Fig. 1). The phages displaying another
24 TNC-C targeting peptide, PL3, also bound to both HESC and 12Z cells (4–6-fold over the insertless phage),
25 followed by the phages displaying iRGD peptide (3- and 9-fold over the insertless for 12Z or HESC,
26 respectively). Only low/background binding to 12Z cells was seen for the RPAR, EM1, and EM2 phages,
27 and RPAR and EM2 showed modest binding to HESC cells (~2-fold over the insertless). EM1 peptide (z13)
28 was identified by *in vivo* phage display on mouse peritoneal cavity and Ishikawa cells²². The receptor for
29 z13 is the cyclic nucleotide-gated channel β 3 (CNGB3), a sorting pathway protein highly expressed in
30 endometrial glandular epithelial cells and peritoneal surfaces in clinical endometriosis samples. EM2
31 peptide was identified by phage biopanning on clinical endometriosis samples and was shown to bind to

1 ectopic endometrial stromal cells²³. It is possible that the receptors for these peptides are not upregulated
2 in the cell culture system used here, or the EM1 and EM2 peptides are context-dependent and some
3 aspects of the T7 peptide display system used here (e.g., C-terminal exposure, peptide density of about
4 200 peptides per 55 nm T7 particle, or linker) are not suited to reveal the efficient binding to the target
5 using the protocols of the current study.

6
7 **Figure 1. Binding of peptide-phages to cultured 12Z and HESC cells.** Cells were incubated with the
8 different peptide-displaying phages at 4 °C for 1 h, washed, and phage binding quantified by plaque assay.
9 The phage binding is represented as a fold over insertless phage. N = 3, error bars = ±SEM. ** p < 0.01,
10 *** p < 0.001 (compared with insertless phage).

11

12 **PL1 receptors are expressed in cultured 12Z and HESC cells**

13 The expression of the receptors recognized by the homing peptides (TNC-C, Fn-EDB, NRP-1, and integrin
14 α_v) in 12Z and HESC cells was studied by confocal microscopy imaging. Confocal microscopy demonstrated
15 that both cells expressed TNC-C and Fn-EDB, α_v integrins and, to a lesser extent, NRP-1 (Fig. 2A). The
16 peptide receptor expression correlated with the peptide-phage binding, with the highest cell binding
17 observed for the ECM targeting peptides, followed by iRGD (integrin $\alpha_v\beta_3/5$ ligand) and RPAR (binding to
18 NRP-1), which is in line with the data on the peptide-displaying phage binding to the cells (Fig. 1).

19 **PL1-targeted nanoparticles internalize in 12Z and HESC cells**

1 In contrast to mono-specific targeting ligands, PL1 engages with two target molecules, Fn-EDB and TNC-
2 C; this engagement is primarily driven by electrostatic interactions³⁵. Simultaneous targeting of two ECM
3 receptors “averages” the accumulation of peptide and its payload over target tissue resulting in more
4 uniform distribution. We have recently shown that PL1 not only binds to the tumor ECM but also
5 internalizes in malignant cells by macropinocytosis³⁵. This feature provides an important advantage over
6 targeting ligands that are reported to be non-internalizing. Firstly, cellular uptake increases the
7 accumulation of the PL1 peptide and its payloads; secondly, cell internalization can dramatically expand
8 the range of PL1 therapeutic payloads to intracellularly-acting cytotoxic agents and radionuclides.

9 We next tested whether PL1-functionalized nanoparticles are internalized in cultured 12Z and HESC cells.
10 AgNP with a size of around 100 nm and Z-potential of -18 mV (Fig. S1), were functionalized with PL1
11 peptide (PL1-AgNPs) and the cellular entry was tested in both cells. Internalized and non-internalized
12 AgNPs can be distinguished by treating the cells with a biocompatible etching solution that eliminates the
13 extracellular AgNPs²⁶. Several studies show that nanoparticles of different core composition (Au, Cd,
14 polymers, lipids, etc.), size range (10 – 150 nm), and surface charge (+30 – -20 mV) accumulate in
15 endometriotic tissue³⁶. The AgNPs that we used here share some features (size ~100 nm, surface
16 PEGylation, and negative Z-potential) with clinically used nanoparticles, such as Caelyx that show
17 enhanced tumor accumulation and long plasma half-life. However, our previous studies demonstrated
18 that peptide-functionalization significantly increased the tumor homing of AgNP^{16,37} and other
19 nanosystems^{37-45,46,47,48} and, therefore, PL1-functionalization might also increase the accumulation of the
20 AgNPs in endometriotic lesions. Biotinylated peptides were coated on neutravidin-functionalized
21 fluorescently labeled AgNPs, and biotin-blocked AgNPs (biotin-AgNPs) were used as a negative control. As
22 both cell lines express NRP-1, a cellular recruitment and internalization receptor of CendR peptides, we
23 also included RPAR as a positive control and a representative of a monospecific peptide that engages with
24 the NRP-1. Moreover, RPAR is also positively charged like PL1. After incubation with AgNPs, the cells were
25 treated with the etching solution and the remaining cell-bound fluorescence was quantified by flow
26 cytometry. After incubation for 2 h, PL1-AgNPs were internalized in both cell lines (Fig. 2B and C), whereas
27 the cells incubated with control biotin-AgNPs remained negative. RPAR-functionalized AgNPs (RPAR-
28 AgNPs) were also internalized in both cell lines, supporting the ability of NRP-1 to take up CendR cargoes.
29 These results show that PL1 and CendR peptides promote the internalization of nanoparticles in 12Z and
30 HESC cells via interaction with proteins of the ECM and the NRP-1 receptor, respectively.

1
2 **Figure 2. Peptide receptor expression and peptide-nanoparticle internalization in 12Z and HESC cells. A)**
3 **Expression of Fn-EDB, TNC-C and cell surface NRP-1 and integrin α_v in attached 12Z and HESC cells.**
4 Attached cells were fixed, incubated with anti-Fn-EDB, anti-TNC-C, anti-NRP-1 or anti-integrin α_v
5 antibodies, and stained with the secondary fluorescent antibodies. Red: Fn-EDB, TNC-C, NRP-1, integrin
6 α_v . Blue: DAPI. Scale bar = 20 μ m. **B and C) Cell internalization of peptide-AgNPs.** Attached cells were
7 incubated with the fluorescently labeled peptide-AgNPs at 37 $^{\circ}$ C for 2 h, treated with the etching solution,
8 detached, and the fluorescence was measured by flow cytometry. N > 4. Error bars = \pm SEM. Panel B shows
9 the number of cells (counts) vs mean fluorescence. Panel C shows the % of fluorescent cells after
10 incubation with the AgNPs. *** p < 0.001 (compared with control biotin-AgNPs).

11

12 **PL1 conjugation increases the effect of cytotoxic nanoparticles in 12Z and HESC cells**

13 Several nanoparticle-based modalities have been developed as nonhormonal therapies for endometriosis,
14 including gene therapy^{49,50,51}, phototherapy^{52,53}, immunotherapy⁵⁴, and combinational therapy⁵⁵. We have

1 also recently demonstrated cell-penetrating peptide and siRNA-mediated therapeutic effects on
2 endometriosis models and proposed a novel therapeutic target, ribonucleotide reductase for the
3 treatment of endometriosis⁵⁶. In addition, we have previously identified miRNAs that are differentially
4 expressed in ectopic endometriotic stromal cells⁵⁷ and found that some anticancer drugs, such as
5 doxorubicin, are selectively cytotoxic to ectopic endometrial cells⁵⁸. Affinity-targeting of such drugs using
6 nanoformulations could be an efficacious strategy to potentiate their activity of specifically depleting
7 endometriotic lesions.

8 Next, we investigated the cytotoxic effect of PL1-AgNPs loaded with the potent antimetabolic agent MMAE
9 (PL1-MMAE-AgNPs)¹⁹. MMAE was loaded onto the AgNPs via a cathepsin B-cleavable valine-citrulline
10 linker. We tested a range of MMAE concentrations to evaluate the peptide-dependent cytotoxicity in 12Z
11 and HESC cells. The cells were incubated with PL1-MMAE-AgNPs or with the untargeted biotin-MMAE-
12 AgNPs at 37 °C for 2 h, washed to remove unbound AgNPs, and incubated for an additional 48 or 72 h (Fig.
13 3). At the highest MMAE concentration (30 nM), the treatment with PL1-MMAE-AgNP resulted in a ~50%
14 decrease in the number of viable 12Z cells and in a ~80% decrease of viable HESC cells. HESC cells appeared
15 more sensitive to the treatment and showed ~35% decrease in viability also at a 6 nM MMAE
16 concentration. In contrast, at the same MMAE concentrations, negative control biotin-MMAE-AgNPs did
17 not have a significant effect on the cell viability. The higher cytotoxic effect observed in HESC compared
18 with 12Z cells, could be due to the different chemosensitivity of endometriotic epithelial and stromal cells,
19 similar to differential chemoresponsiveness observed between malignant epithelial and stromal cells of
20 malignant carcinomas⁵⁹. These results show that the PL1-guided therapeutic nanoparticles are able to
21 efficiently deliver an intracellularly-acting drug inside the 12Z and HESC cells.

22 To bind MMAE to AgNPs we used a valine-citrulline linker that is cathepsin B sensitive. Some ECM
23 proteases, such as matrix metalloproteinases, are overexpressed in ectopic endometrial tissue^{60,61}. It is
24 possible that application of alternative enzyme-cleavable linkers might result in increased release of the
25 drug in endometriotic lesions.

1

2 **Figure 3. PL1 conjugation increases the cytotoxicity of MMAE-AgNPs.** Attached 12Z and HESC cells were
 3 incubated with different concentrations of PL1-MMAE-AgNPs or biotin-MMAE-NPs at 37 °C for 2 h,
 4 washed and incubated for an additional 48 or 72 h. The cytotoxicity was measured using the CellTiter-
 5 Glo® viability assay. The cytotoxicity is represented as a percentage of viability relative to the untreated
 6 cells. N = 5, error bars = ±SEM, ***p < 0.001.

7

8 **PL1 promotes the penetration and cytotoxicity of AgNPs in endometriotic spheroids**

9 We next studied the cellular internalization and penetration of PL1-AgNPs into 12Z spheroids. Three-
 10 dimensional cell culture mimics the properties of tissues better than the regular monolayer cultures⁶².
 11 Compared to 12Z epithelial cells grown as 2D monolayers, 3D 12Z spheroids are morphologically and
 12 functionally more similar to the actual clinical lesions⁶³.

13 The spheroids were incubated with fluorescent PL1-AgNPs or nontargeted AgNPs (biotin-AgNPs) for
 14 different times, treated with the etching solution to remove exposed AgNPs, and imaged by confocal
 15 fluorescence microscopy. Microscopic imaging of the central core and peripheral rim of the spheroids

1 showed that at 2 and 4 h of incubation the PL1-AgNPs were internalized in the spheroid cells at the
2 periphery of the spheroids (Fig. 4A). After 20 h of incubation, PL1-AgNPs were also found deeper in the
3 spheroids (Fig. 4A, white arrow). In contrast, biotin-AgNPs did not bind and penetrate the spheroids.

4 Next, the effect of PL1-MMAE-AgNPs on the integrity and viability of 12Z spheroids was evaluated. The
5 integrity of the spheroids treated with PL1-MMAE-AgNPs was compromised already after 24 h of
6 incubation. The damage, seen as loss of the compact structure and blebbing, became more pronounced
7 after 48 h (Fig. 4B). In contrast, the untreated spheroids or spheroids treated with biotin-MMAE-AgNPs
8 showed no damage and continued growing until the 72 h time point. The viability of 12Z cells in 3D culture
9 was also tested at 72 h of incubation with different concentrations of PL1- and biotin-MMAE-AgNPs. The
10 quantitation of the viable cells in spheroids after 72 h treatment showed that in comparison to spheroids
11 treated with biotin-MMAE-AgNPs, PL1-MMAE-AgNP-treated spheroids had ~20% decrease in the number
12 of viable cells at 60 nM of drug (Fig. 4C). These data show that PL1 induces the internalization and cytotoxic
13 effect of nanoparticles in 3D culture of endometriotic cells.

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1
2 **Figure 4. PL1 conjugation increases the penetration and internalization of AgNPs in 12Z spheroids and**
3 **the cytotoxicity of MMAE-AgNPs. A) Penetration and internalization of PL1-AgNPs in 12Z spheroids.** The
4 spheroids were incubated with fluorescently labeled PL1-AgNPs or biotin-AgNPs for 1, 2, 4, and 20 h, and
5 the internalized AgNPs were detected by confocal fluorescence microscopy. Red = AgNPs; Blue = DAPI.
6 Scale bar = 100 μ m. **B) Morphology of spheroids after incubation with PL1-MMAE-NP or biotin-MMAE-**
7 **AgNPs.** Representative images of 12Z spheroids incubated for 24, 48 and 72 h with the AgNPs. Scale bar
8 = 100 μ m. **C) Toxicity of PL1-MMAE-AgNPs in 12Z spheroids.** Spheroids were incubated with different
9 concentrations of PL1-MMAE-AgNPs or biotin-MMAE-AgNPs for 72 h, and the cell viability was measured
10 by the CellTiter-Glo[®] viability assay. N = 3. Error bars = \pm SEM. *p < 0.05.

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1 **PL1-AgNPs bind to TNC-C- and Fn-EDB-positive areas of human peritoneal endometriotic lesions.**

2 To assess the translational potential of PL1-mediated targeting, the *ex vivo* binding of PL1-AgNPs and the
3 expression of PL1 peptide's receptors TNC-C and Fn-EDB were evaluated in clinical peritoneal
4 endometriosis samples. First, the endometriotic lesion sites in the clinical sample were mapped by
5 immunohistochemistry. The staining for CD10, a marker of ectopic endometrial stroma⁶⁴, demonstrated
6 the presence of a large endometriotic gland surrounded by stroma in the peritoneal tissue (Fig. 5, black
7 arrow). TNC-C immunoreactivity localized to the epithelial cells of the endometriotic gland (Fig. 5, white
8 arrow) but not to the glands of eutopic endometrium. Fn-EDB was also detected in the peritoneal
9 endometriosis sample but not in the eutopic endometrium (Fig. 5, white arrowhead), indicating a
10 differential TNC-C and Fn-EDB expression in ectopic and eutopic endometrial tissues. TNC-C and Fn-EDB
11 signal was observed in areas around the CD31-positive blood vessels (Fig. 5, black arrowhead). After
12 incubating the cryosections with PL1-AgNPs and washing, we observed nanoparticles in endometriotic
13 lesions in the perivascular areas positive for the expression of TNC-C and Fn-EDB (Fig. 5, white
14 arrowheads), while no signal was seen in the eutopic endometrium. This result suggests that PL1 targets
15 not only ectopic endometriotic cells but also neovessels surrounding the endometriotic lesions, thus
16 further demonstrating the advantage of using PL1-AgNPs as a theranostic tool.

17

18

19 **Figure 5. Clinical peritoneal endometriotic lesions express TNC-C and Fn-EDB, and PL1-AgNPs bind to**
20 **the endometriotic lesions.** Human peritoneal endometriotic lesion and human eutopic endometrium
21 samples were cryosectioned and immunostained with Fn-EDB, TNC-C, CD10, and CD31 or incubated with

1 fluorescently labeled PL1-AgNPs or control AgNPs. The control AgNPs binding is shown in Fig. S2. Red:
2 TNC-C (white arrow), Fn-EDB (white arrowhead), PL1-AgNP (white arrowhead); brown: CD10 (black
3 arrow), CD31 (black arrowhead); blue: DAPI or hematoxylin. Scale bar = 150 μ m.

4

5 **CONCLUSION**

6 PL1 homing peptide has the potential to be positioned as an enabling technology both in endometriosis
7 diagnostics (e.g., guided surgery, imaging) as well as therapeutics, expanding the therapeutic index of
8 drugs by maximizing efficacy and limiting systemic side effects. Our results encourage further studies for
9 their preclinical development. The *in vivo* homing of the PL1-targeted nanoparticles to endometriosis
10 lesions and their therapeutic effect in animal models as well as the exploration of different therapeutic
11 and imaging cargoes will be the subjects of follow-up studies.

12

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19

20 **AUTHOR'S CONTRIBUTION**

21 LSG and KK are co-first authors. Conceptualization, TT, LSG, KK, and PL; Methodology, KK, LSG, VP, AT, TT,
22 and PL; Validation, KK, LSG, and VP; Formal Analysis, LSG, KK, and VP; Investigation, KK, LSG, VP, AT;
23 Resources, TT, AS, MP, and MS; Data Curation, LSG, KK, and VP; Writing – Original Draft Preparation, LSG,
24 KK, TT, VP, and AT; Writing – Review & Editing, TT, LSG, KK, VP, AT, PL, AS, MP; Supervision, TT; Funding
25 Acquisition, TT and AS.

26

27 **CONFLICT OF INTEREST**

1 TT is an inventor of iRGD and CendR peptides and a shareholder of Cend Therapeutics Inc., a company
2 that holds a license for the CendR peptides. TT and PL hold a patent on PL1 peptide (“Bi-Specific
3 Extracellular Matrix Binding Peptides and Methods of Use Thereof”; WO. patent no. WO 2020/161602 A1.
4

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